

Petrochemical Characteristics of the Igneous Rocks Exposed in the Nanyaseik Area, Hpakant Township, Kachin State, Northern Myanmar

Htin Lynn Aung*, Thaire Phyu Win**, Khin Maung Hla***

Abstract

Nanyaseik area is situated on the main road from Mogaung, Kamaing to Hpakant under the administration of Hpakant Township, Kachin State. It is bounded by North Latitudes ($25^{\circ} 36' - 25^{\circ} 43'$) and East Longitudes ($96^{\circ} 30' - 96^{\circ} 36'$) in one inch topographic map index of 92C/10. The main lithologic units comprise metamorphic and igneous rock. The igneous rocks are mainly microgranite and serpentinite. The analysis of major elements in some rocks was determined by XRF spectrometer and interpreted the genesis of these rock units. On the basis of the petrochemical characteristics, the microgranite in the study area is I-type granitoid formed by partial melting of mantle. It carried rare elements and hydrothermal sulfide ore veins which cut all preexisting lithologies.

Key words: Nanyaseik area, I-type, partial melting, rare elements.

Introduction

Nanyaseik area is situated in Hpakant Township, Myitkyina District, Kachin State. It is bounded by Latitudes $25^{\circ} 36'$ to $25^{\circ} 43'$ N and Longitudes $96^{\circ} 30'$ to $96^{\circ} 36'$ E in one inch topographic map index of 92 C/10. The Nanya area is accessible by car from Mogaung, which is located on the Mandalay-Myitkyina highway and railway. The location map of the study area is shown in (Fig.1).

Purpose of Study

This paper is mainly intended to establish the petrogenesis of the igneous rocks based on the petrochemical analysis.

Fig.1 Location Map of the Nanyaseik Area.

* Dr., Lecturer, Department of Geology, Bago University

** Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Geology, Yadanabon University

*** Dr., Professor & Head of Department of Geology, Bago University

Materials and Methods

The geochemical results for 5 samples of microgranite were sent to the Department of Technology Promotion and Coordination, Metallurgical Research and Development Center, Ela. Major elements of whole-rock analyses were determined by wavelength dispersive XRF spectrometer.

General Geology

The study area mainly comprises the igneous and metamorphic rocks. The igneous rocks are microgranite and serpentinite. Regionally, jade mine area is situated in western part of the area occupying basic and ultramafic igneous rocks. The north-south trending Sagaing fault (right-lateral strike slip fault) regarded as a trench link fault (Dey, 1972; Win Swe, 1972; Myint Thein et. al., 1981, 1983) probably ceases its dextral displacement near the area of Indawgyi Lake and bifurcates northward and eastward into Taikri and Namyin faults.

Results

Nomenclature of Granitoid Rocks

Based on the composition, they are evaluated and plotted in the QAP diagram (Fig. 2). Due to this classification and using normative contents of quartz, alkali feldspar and plagioclase feldspar, the igneous rocks of the study area comprise quartz-rich granitoid (microgranite) and microdiorite.

Fig. 2 Plotted data of the igneous rocks of the study area.
(Source: IUGS Classification, 2006)

Chemical Characteristics of Igneous Rocks

The igneous rocks in the study area are microgranites and microdiorite. They have approximately, 45 – 69% SiO₂. These rocks, in general, have Al₂O₃ (12.64 - 35.15 Wt %), TiO₂ (0.5 - 0.7 Wt %), CaO (0.3 - 3.4 Wt %), MgO (1.84 - 4.91 Wt %), Na₂O + K₂O (5.55 - 10.47 Wt %). Major element oxides (Al₂O₃, CaO, MgO, TiO₂, FeO, Fe₂O₃ and Na₂O) are negatively correlated with the SiO₂ in Harker diagrams (Figs. 3 and 4) with the exception of K₂O (positively correlated with SiO₂). Harker diagrams (Fig. 4) using major elements (Al, Na, Ca, K, Mg, Ti and Fe) are used to interpret the behavior of the elements using SiO₂ as an index for igneous fractionation. The content of Al₂O₃ is higher in the microgranite favours the growth of corundum.

In the molecular Al₂O₃-CaO-(Na₂O+K₂O) and Al₂O₃ / (CaO + K₂O + Na₂O), i.e. A/CNK versus FeO / (FeO + MgO) diagram (Figs. 5 and 6), the compositions mostly plot into the peraluminous domains of Shand (1974). K₂O – Na₂O – CaO plot also shows a decrease of K₂O with enrichment in Na₂O during the initial stage of differentiation. In the later stage of magmatic evolution, the trend shows an increase of CaO with depletion of Na₂O (Figs. 7 and 8). According to ACF diagram, the granitoids from the Nanyaseik area is fitted within the model of I-type field (Fig. 9).

Fig. 3 Na₂O/K₂O vs SiO₂ variation diagram, showing the trend of differentiation.

Tectonic Discrimination of Granitic Rocks

The tectonic setting of granitic rocks from the study area was studied by making use of the major elements with reference to (Maniar and Piccoli, 1989).

K₂O vs SiO₂ variation diagram (Fig. 10) shows that all microgranites fall within the field of CAG + CCG and a microdiorite falls within the field of RRG + CEUG.

Al₂O₃ vs SiO₂ variation diagram (Fig. 11) also shows the same field as in K₂O vs SiO₂. MgO vs SiO₂ variation diagram (Fig. 12) shows that the three microgranites fall within the field of CAG + CCG and the rest one falls within the field of POG and microdiorite falls within the field of RRG + CEUG.

Shand's index diagram indicates the distinction between CAG and CCG. According to Shand's index diagram, all microgranites in the study area are confined to the CCG field (Fig. 13).

Fig. 4 Variation diagram of major elements vs SiO₂ in igneous rocks of the study area.

Fig. 5 Al₂O₃-CaO-(Na₂O+K₂O) plot of the igneous rocks of the area.

Fig. 6 FeO/(FeO+MgO) vs Al₂O₃ / (CaO+Na₂O+K₂O) plot of the igneous rocks of the area.

Fig. 7 Fe₂O₃-Na₂O + K₂O-MgO diagram showing the evolution curve, differentiation within a series is indicated by the arrow.

Fig. 8 Na₂O-K₂O-CaO diagram showing the evolutionary trend of igneous rocks. Differentiation within a series is indicated by the arrow.

Fig. 9 ACF diagram for the granitoids of the study area (after Hine et al., 1978); Molar ratio : A = Al₂O₃ - Na₂O-K₂O, C=CaO, F = FeO + MgO.

Fig. 10 K₂O vs SiO₂ diagram showing the distinction between other granitoids from the other environment.

Fig. 11 Al₂O₃ vs SiO₂ diagram for granitoids of the study area.

Fig. 15 Shand's index diagram for granitoids (Continental collision granitoids) and CAG (Continental arc granitoids).

Conclusion

Based on the normative contents of quartz, alkali feldspar and plagioclase feldspar, the igneous rocks are microgranite and microdiorite. Major element oxides (Al_2O_3 , CaO , MgO , TiO_2 , FeO , Fe_2O_3 and Na_2O) are negatively correlated with the SiO_2 in Harker diagrams with the exception of K_2O (positively correlated with SiO_2). In the molecular Al_2O_3 - CaO - $(\text{Na}_2\text{O}+\text{K}_2\text{O})$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/(\text{CaO} + \text{K}_2\text{O} + \text{Na}_2\text{O})$, i.e. A/CNK versus $\text{FeO}/(\text{FeO} + \text{MgO})$ diagram, the compositions plot in peraluminous domains. K_2O - Na_2O - CaO plot shows decrease of K_2O with enrichment in Na_2O during the initial stage of differentiation. In the later stage, the trend shows increase of CaO with depletion of Na_2O . According to ACF diagram, the granitoids are fitted within I-type field. K_2O vs SiO_2 diagram shows that all microgranites fall within the field of CAG + CCG and a microdiorite falls within the field of RRG + CEUG. Al_2O_3 vs SiO_2 diagram also shows the same field as in K_2O vs SiO_2 . On the basis of the petrochemical characteristics, the microgranite in the study area is I-type granitoid formed by partial melting of mantle.

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References

- Dey, B.P., (1972). *Aerial photo interpretation of a major lineament in the Yamethin-Pyawbwe Quadrangle – Sci. Technol. Burma*, 1st Burma Res. Congr. (1966). Vol.1, No.3, p.431-443, Rangoon.
- Hine. R.J.S. Williams, B.W. Chappell, and A.J.R. White. (1978). *Contrasts between I-type and S-type granitoids of the Kosciusko batholiths*, J. Geol. Soc. Aust., vol.25, pp. 219-234.
- IUGS Classification. (2006). *IUGS nomenclature of plutonic rocks*.
- Maniar, P.D., Piccoli, P.M. (1989). *Tectonic discrimination of Granitoids*. Geol. Soc. Am. Bull., v.101, p.635-643.
- Myint Thein et.al. (1981). *On the lateral displacement of the Sagaing Fault*. Department of Geology. Mandalay University (Unpublished).
- Myint Thein et.al. (1983). *Geology of the area between Tigyaing and Katha*. Unpublished. Department of Geology. University of Mandalay.
- Shand. (1974). *Shand's index diagram for granitoid rocks*.
- Win Swe. (1972). *Strike-Slip faulting in Central Belt of Burma*. In Regional Conf. geology Mineral Resources Southeast Asia. (Edited by Haile. N.S) Annex: Geol: Soc. Malaysia Newsletter.